

Studies in Condensed Phosphates. Part IV. Sodium Metaphosphate and its Derivatives with Lithium

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Derivatives with the general formulae $(\text{Na}_x \text{Li}_{1-x} \text{PO}_3)_n$ have been prepared where $x=2/3, 1/3,$ or $1/2$. The physico-chemical properties of these complex derivatives have been compared with simple sodium metaphosphate glass.

Although the chemistry of sodium metaphosphate has been studied more thoroughly than that of any other phosphate glasses, little work has been mentioned about the Li, K, and Cs glasses¹. The behaviour of lithium phosphate glasses is more or less similar to that of sodium phosphate glass, but potassium phosphate melts definitely differ markedly in properties. The mixed glasses of sodium with divalent cations, particularly calcium, have been reported earlier² from these laboratories. Lithium, although it belongs to the first group, shows striking similarity to calcium, for example, lithium orthophosphate is insoluble in water. In view of the above, it was interesting to make an investigation of the properties of lithium metaphosphate glasses $(\text{LiPO}_3)_n$ and also of mixed derivatives of the type $(\text{Na}_x \text{Li}_{1-x} \text{PO}_3)_n$, where x is $1/3, 2/3,$ or $1/2$.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents used were of pure grade. A Gallenkamp muffle furnace was used for preparing the samples. Philips magic eye conductivity bridge was used at 1000 c.p.s. for measuring the resistances. A fixed parallel plate conductivity cell was used. The temperature was maintained for all measurements at $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$ unless mentioned otherwise. All readings were taken after 24 hours' dissolution³ in order to attain equilibrium. Extra pure water was taken for preparation of the solution. Cambridge pH meter was taken for measuring pH. A Carl-Zeiss flame photometer was used for analysing sodium in the compounds.

Lithium phosphate glasses were prepared as earlier³ by heating the mixture of lithium carbonate and diammonium hydrogen orthophosphate according to the equation:

Clear transparent melt was chilled in between stainless steel plates.

1. "Phosphorus and its Compounds", Vol. I, 1958, p. 791, Interscience Publishers Inc., New York.
2. Mehrotra and Gupta, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1961, 54, 613.
3. Wazer *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, 54, 777.

The mixed derivatives of the general formula $(\text{Na}_x\text{M}_{1-x}\text{PO}_3)_n$, where M is lithium and x is 2/3, 1/2, or 1/3, have been prepared according to the equation :

The chilled melt is transparent and glassy in appearance, similar to that of sodium phosphate melt. The precipitating behaviour of $(\text{LiPO}_3)_n$ melt was seen with divalent metal salts, such as, CaCl_2 , BaCl_2 , SrCl_2 , MgSO_4 , and PbSO_4 . Like $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ solutions, the precipitate is formed and is readily soluble in excess of lithium phosphate solution.

Measurement of Conductance.—The conductances of solutions of mixed sodium lithium metaphosphates prepared at 800° are recorded in Table I. Similarly, the conductance of the solutions of $(\text{LiPO}_3)_n$ is compared in the same table with $(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$ solutions. The results of Table I are plotted in Figs. 1-3 in three different ways:

- (1) Specific conductance against concentration.
- (2) Log equivalent conductance against log concentration.
- (3) Equivalent conductance against square root of concentration.

The formal concentrations of all solutions have been calculated taking the formula weight of the compound containing one (PO_3) unit as the formal weight.

TABLE I

Specific conductance $\times 10^4$ at $30^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$.

Solutions of f/33.33 diluted to 50 ml.	$(\text{NaPO}_3)_n$.	$(\text{LiPO}_3)_n$.	$(\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Li}_{1/3}\text{PO}_3)_n$.	$(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Li}_{1/2}\text{PO}_3)_n$.	$(\text{Na}_{1/3}\text{Li}_{2/3}\text{PO}_3)_n$
1	0.3934	0.4056	0.4013	0.3949	0.4193
2	0.6637	0.6784	0.6847	0.6694	0.7463
5	1.4600	1.4350	1.5320	1.4350	1.6190
10	2.5960	2.5640	2.7140	2.5390	2.6050
15	3.7050	3.5720	3.7500	3.5540	3.6470
20	4.6970	4.4950	4.8460	4.5510	4.9100
25	5.6970	5.4080	5.7850	5.5290	5.9460
30	6.5240	6.3760	6.7230	6.4330	6.9740
35	7.4840	7.3160	7.6140	7.3160	7.9980
40	8.3520	8.1120	8.7800	8.3390	8.9910

Note : The temperature of the preparation of the above derivatives is $800^\circ \pm 25^\circ$.

Determination of Molecular Weights

(a) *By Viscosity Method (M_w).*—An Ostwald viscometer having a time flow for water 100-150 seconds was used for viscosity measurements. The reduced viscosity η_{sp}/C (where $\eta_{sp} = \eta_s/\eta_0 - 1$, η_s and η_0 being the viscosity of solution and solvent respectively and C , the concentration of the polymer in g./100 ml) is plotted against concentration and the value of $(\eta_{sp}/C)_{C \rightarrow 0}$ is determined by extrapolation. For calculating the molecular weight, the following simple formula has been employed:

$$(\eta_{sp}/C)_{C \rightarrow 0} = [\eta] = KM_w$$

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The value of K is given by Strauss *et al.*⁴ from light scattering measurements in sodium bromide solutions to be 1.76×10^{-5} and M_w is the weight average molecular weight. Sodium chloride was taken as supporting electrolyte in the present study, as given in an earlier publication⁵ by us and its concentration was taken to be $0.035N$. The plots of $(\eta_{sp}/C)_{c \rightarrow 0}$, were straight line as given by others^{4,6} and confirmed by us⁵. Table II shows the relationship between the weight average and number average molecular weights.

TABLE II

Relationship between number average molecular weight (M_n) and weight average molecular weight (M_w).

Compounds.	Temp. of preparation.	M_n .	M_w .
$(\text{LiPO}_3)_n$	800°	3077	7680
$(\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Li}_{1/3}\text{PO}_3)_n$	800°	4650	7350
	700°	3100	6660
$(\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{Li}_{1/2}\text{PO}_3)_n$	800°	5000	8000
$(\text{Na}_{1/3}\text{Li}_{2/3}\text{PO}_3)_n$	800°	3200	6890

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3935.

5. *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1961, **55**, 81.

6. Chatterjee and Bhargava, *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, **160**, 35.

FIG. 5

FIG. 4

TABLE III

Temperature of preparation=800°.

Compounds.	Conc.	η_{sp}/C .	$[\eta]$.	M_w .
$(LiPO_3)_n$	0.2	0.1350		
	0.4	0.1350	0.1350	
	0.6	0.1360		7670
	0.8	0.1350		
$(Na_{1/3}Li_{2/3}PO_3)_n$	0.2	0.1210		
	0.4	0.1212	0.1212	
	0.6	0.1216		6888
	0.8	0.1213		
$(Na_{1/2}Li_{1/2}PO_3)_n$	0.2	0.1308		
	0.4	0.1308	0.1400	
	0.6	0.1400		8000
	0.8	0.1400		
$(Na_{2/3}Li_{1/3}PO_3)_n$	0.116	0.1293		
	0.174	0.1290	0.1293	
	0.232	0.1291		7350
	0.290	0.1292		

(b) *By End Group Method (M_n).*—A simple equation derived on the assumption⁷ that there is one hydroxy group at each end of the polymer chain:

$$M_n = \frac{20000 \times \text{weight of the sample in g.}}{\text{ml of } N/10\text{-NaOH}}$$

(pH range 4.5 to 9.0) requires two equivalents of alkali per g. mole of the polymer. The results are plotted in Figs. 4 and 5.

DISCUSSION

It appears from Table I that $(LiPO_3)_n$ and its mixed compounds are very closely similar to that of $(NaPO_3)_n$. This clearly indicates that Li ions themselves and in mixed conditions behave similarly as sodium ions and hence its properties can be studied on similar grounds. The different plots given in Figs. 1-3 show a typical behaviour of polyelectrolytic character discussed already and can be explained on the same lines as has been observed by us² as well as by other workers⁸; the number average molecular weights, determined by end group titration methods, are lower than weight average molecular weights in the case of simple sodium metaphosphate glasses; the same relationship between the above two values appears to hold for pure lithium as well as lithium sodium mixed glasses. This relationship was reversed in the case of sodium-calcium mixed glasses and was explained by a greater lowering of the viscosity caused by bivalent calcium ions available by secondary dissociation. The

7. Gustavson and Larsson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1951, 5, 1221.

8. Straus and Trietler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 77, 1473; Chatterjee and Bhaigava, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1959, 35, 235; Bawn, "The Chemistry of High Polymers", Interscience Publishers, New York, U.S.A., 1948, p. 35.

lithium ions, being monovalent, will have the same order of effect as sodium ions and hence this appears to confirm the conclusions arrived in the case of sodium calcium metaphosphate glasses.

One of the authors (V. S. G.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship during the tenure of this work.

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Received December 6, 1961.